

Sustainable Energy Harvesting Systems Based on Innovative Mine Waste Recycling

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2 ABBREVIATIONS AND ACRONYMS

Acronym	Description
DCP	Dissemination and Communication Plan (for START)
D&C	Dissemination and Communication
ExCom	START's Executive Committee (WP leaders)
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
WP	Work Package
PM	Powder Metallurgy
TEG	ThermoElectric Generators

3 EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The present deliverable fulfils the requirement of demonstrating the **development of a Dissemination and Communication Plan (DCP)**, in its initial version, that will lead the activity of WP6 “Dissemination and Communication” also in relationship with the other WPs, and that will be updated during the project to guarantee flexibility and optimisation of D&C efforts, as measured via the selected KPIs.

The DCP contains an outline of all the activities envisaged within the project for D&C, including the various procedures for publications, to monitor the performance of the D&C effort, etc.

The DCP will be reviewed regularly, and at least twice during the project (at M24 and M48).

4 INTRODUCTION: DISSEMINATION AND COMMUNICATION PRINCIPLES

In the original proposal, the START consortium already indicated the principles upon which the Dissemination and Communication plan, a “document outlining the most efficient strategy and means for implementing the dissemination and communication” activities, would be based:

- **Publication process:** Consortium partners are entitled and incited to publish results in the usual scientific form. A list of relevant open access journals and conferences will be collectively established at the project start. The Dissemination and Communication Plan will establish the publication rules and guidelines. All foreseen publications will follow a validation process (to avoid conflicts or nullifying patent applications).
- **Transparency:** All public results and deliverables will be accessible through the project website.
- **Accessibility and knowledge management:** The ambition is for START to become a knowledge hub. This requires an active strategy of knowledge brokerage and structuring lessons learned. Properly structured this will provide synergies with other initiatives, avoiding duplication, strengthening impact and delivering value for money. Three levels of dissemination are foreseen:
 - Consortium
 - broader START community, and
 - fully publicly disclosed.
- **Building knowledge capacity:** Webinars, seminars and a final Workshop will be organised to support knowledge transfer and capacity development. They will target a wide range of actors and will showcase the project, share knowledge and build partnerships. Further influence will be achieved through social media channels to broadcast the key outcomes and opportunities arising from these activities.
- **Engagement strategy:** The Dissemination and Communication Plan will deliver a communication and engagement strategy, guidelines, graphical identity and supporting material. The strategy will align with the principle of Horizon Europe and EU directives to demonstrate the value-added benefits of project and their wider social benefits. This will use include the following elements: target audience segmentation; delivery channels including social media; calendar of events; key thematic messages; contextualised and culturally sensitive communications; multi-lingual messaging; serious online game.
- **Differentiated delivery channels:** Differentiated delivery channels will ensure active engagement at broad level. The core audience groups within the communications strategy are as follows:
 - Group 1 - Policy makers and influencers concerned with the green transition and sustainable circular economy at European level.
 - Group 2 - Economically active entrepreneurs and industrial actors at European level.
 - Group 3 - Scientific community across the geology, materials science, renewable energy.
 - Group 4 - General public across the EU.

Based on these principles, during these first weeks of the project EPMA, LNEG, ASGMI, LPRC and the other consortium members worked to define the actual Dissemination and Communication

plan. It includes many chapters and covers all the D&C strategy. A policy on its monitoring and update has also been imagined.

Some details had already been indicated in the proposal text (Table 1).

Table 1: Tools for Dissemination and Communication as indicated in the proposal.

Tool	Purpose	Audience	Due	Quantified target
Project Graphical Identity	A Graphical Identity for the START project (logo and general branding colour schemes, for the website, the social media, mail signatures for partners, and all other uses) will be developed in the first months.	All	M02	-
Project website	Main channel for information and major tool for the visibility of the START activities. Updated frequently, with a blend of status, push and active content including: project overview; public documents; agenda; articles and news; multimedia. Individuals can also use the website to sign up to the newsletter and social media channels.	All groups	M02 onwards	Visitors: 2000 in year 1 rising to at least 4000 in year 4
Social media	LinkedIn, YouTube and Twitter will be considered as main dissemination channels, Slideshare and Twitch as secondary dissemination channels. LinkedIn supports community management with restricted fora. A YouTube channel will be used to engage with a broader audience by sharing videos, including an introduction to START, short interviews, and selected partner videos.	All groups	M02 onwards	Twitter: 1000 followers in year 1, rising to 2500 by the end of the project LinkedIn: 800 followers by the end of the project.
Videos	Some videos are planned for various uses: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A short generic video (0.5-1 min) with simple information, to be used for general awareness about START. • A mid-term longer video, highlighting preliminary project results. • 2 or more short videos focused on different subtopics within the project, with examples of improvements achieved within the project. • A short generic video (0.5-1 min) with simple information, to be used as a summary of the results obtained in START. 	Groups 1-4 1-3 2-3 1-4	M04 M24 M48 M48	Average of 200 views per video (at least 100 total views)
Newsletters	A public biannual newsletter will be circulated to individuals who sign up. The newsletter will include a summary of the activities over a 6-month period.	Groups 1-3	M06 onwards	Demand led but minimum of 500 per semester
Webinars/ seminars/ workshop	Communication of the project outcomes and activities, to share knowledge, ideas and updates.	Groups 2, 3	M06 onwards	Audience of 100 per event
Serious online game	A serious online game for capacity building on raw materials, sustainability and circular economy.	All groups	M24 onwards	Visitors: 300
Other publications	Articles on web-based innovation news services, like the Horizon Magazine, Cordis, and on commercial magazines like Open Access Management	All groups	M06 onwards	Total reach >400000

5 DISSEMINATION AND COMMUNICATION PLAN - INITIAL VERSION

In the following, the initial version of the Dissemination and Communication Plan (in short, DCP), is explained. All the activities presently imagined for the project, and the normal rules to carry them out, are here outlined.

5.1 TARGET AUDIENCE SEGMENTATION

The audience for the project topics has been segmented in 4 groups, depending on their role and possible interactivity with the project:

- **Group 1** - Policy makers and influencers concerned with the green transition and sustainable circular economy at European level. This group includes, local, regional, country and EU level political figures, especially those in charge and influential in all relevant policies concerning industry, minerals and mining, energy, supply chains, sustainability, and potentially all journalists, web- or print-based, all social media (LinkedIn, Twitter, YouTube) influential people dealing with scientific, mining, resources, industrial, energy and sustainability topics.
- **Group 2** - Economically active entrepreneurs and industrial actors at European level in the three main segments of the value chain:
 - a. Raw material suppliers (mining sector)
 - b. TEG device producers (thermoelectric industry)
 - c. TEG utilisers (i.e., waste heat producers)
- **Group 3** - Scientific community across the geology, materials science, thermoelectric energy harvesting, renewable energy
- **Group 4** – General public across the EU

For maximum efficacy, the D&C activities will have to address each target groups with the correct approach.

For instance, **Group 1** will not be intrigued by the technical details, but rather by the possible impact of the project on social and industrial conditions. The D&C channels will include, for example, the participation in major events promoted by public authorities like the Raw Materials Week or the European Sustainable Energy Week for presenting the project, its results and the expected impact in economy and society. This will have two main objectives. Firstly, raise awareness of the need to establish policies related to the valorisation of secondary raw materials, the circular economy and of sustainable energy ecosystems, where waste-heat energy harvesting systems play an important role. Secondly, to induce a favourable economic and political environment for START technologies deployment in the market.

Group 2 will need to be interested by showing the economic potential of the materials and technologies developed, again with limited interested in the technicalities. The D&C channels will focus on the publication of project summaries and news in the START newsletter, as well as in newsletters from relevant associations, such as those from EPMA, EIT (European Institute of Innovation & Technology), EGS (EuroGeoSurveys) or ETS (European Thermoelectric Society). Other activities will include the participation in events organized by these associations, organisation

of workshops for potential customers and publication of articles in technical and sectorial magazines. The main objectives with these D&C activities are:

- a) to provide information on START technologies to industrial actors and other entrepreneurs.
- b) to foster technology acceptance by end users.
- c) to collect key information about the target market to increase exploitation opportunities.

Group 3 will on the other hand be interested in actual science behind the results and this includes, for example, a more in-depth discussion of the structure and properties, all the way to the technical-scientific details of a life cycle analysis. The D&C channels will cover, for example, the publication of scientific articles in open access journals and online repositories and participation in scientific international conferences. This will help to increase knowledge about project developments and to capitalize on the results in new research and innovation activities.

Group 4 needs the less technical and most emotional storytelling, as they mostly have no specific scientific background and include older and younger people, and children. The aim here is to contribute to improving the awareness of the general public across the EU on energy and raw materials sustainability issues and about the proposed solutions brought by the START project, enabling a faster acceptance of the products generated within the project. The activities will include the serious game, the START comics and the participation in Science Festivals and Fairs.

In addition to this segmentation, languages should be considered, so for instance if an external event is carried out in Spanish or another language, a specific translation should be prepared, especially if the target is not highly educated.

Similarly, messages will need to be tuned to the type of event or media chosen: a presentation in a “mining” community will have to be different from one given in an “energy” or “material science” community. The extreme will be when addressing common people, for instance in a Science Fair open to public, that is the target group 4. For this, quite easy and pictorial presentations will have to be used, where the technical details normally should not be present.

5.2 EVENTS

In order to select the events where the partners, individually or as consortium, should take part, and take materials concerning the project, a “**START Events List**” is established and regularly updated by the WP6 leader (EPMA) on the START SharePoint and every partner will collaborate by giving information on possible events.

In this Excel file, the following information is collected for each event:

- Name of Event
- Priority: the partners are asked to evaluate what is the priority to give to this event in order to try maximising the impact by optimising the effort.
- Date of start of event
- Date of end of event
- Physical/Online/Hybrid: if available, information on the type of participation requested.
- Website: where possible, the link to obtain fresh info about the event
- Location: where the event will be held (in case, “online”)

- Type of audience: scientific (what sector), industrial (what sector), general (what composition) etc.
- START Booth: whether a START booth should be present at the event
- Partner Booth: whether a START partner booth should be present at the event (including name of partner)
- START lectures/papers: in case a presentation is given, details on the topic (e.g., “Generic project presentation” or a specific topic)
- START lecture/paper date: when the presentation will happen
- Presenter: who is going to present
- Reference partner: the partner who will be coordinating the participation
- Attendees: expected number of attendees

The list will be the basis for discussion, in the meetings, about participation at the various events.

In Figure 1 the present status of the list is shown.

Event	Priority	Date start	Date end	Physical/ Online/ Web	Website	Location	Type of audience	START Booth	Partner Booth	START lectures/papers	START lecture/paper date	Presenter	Reference partner	Attendees
EGT Raw Materials Summit (every year around April/May)		2022, May		Physical	https://www.egtsummit.com/									
EGU - European Geoscience Union (every year around April/May)		2022, May		Physical	https://www.egu.eu/									
PCAO - Prospector & Developer Association of Canada		2022, Jun		Physical	https://www.pcao.ca/									
Sustainable Minerals '22		11/07/2022	13/07/2022	Online	https://min.eurochem.com/sustainable-minerals-22/									
Desafíos para la gestión sostenible de los pasivos ambientales mineros ECLAC-CEPAL, United Nations		01/08/2022	04/08/2022	Physical		Perú				presentation		Freddy Guzman, Che ASAMI		
The Ceramics Expo 2022		29/08/2022	31/08/2022	Physical	https://www.ceramicsexpo.com/	Huntington Convention Center of Cleveland, Ohio (USA)	PII community	-	GenCore					
International Materials, Applications and Technologies (IMAT) - ASM 2022		12/09/2022	15/09/2022	Physical	https://www.asmmaterials.com/asm2022/	New Orleans, Louisiana (USA)	PII community, Academic	-	GenCore	presentation		Danien Kasowicz, GenCore		
European Conference on Thermoelectrics (ECT) 2022		14/09/2022	16/09/2022	Physical	http://www.ec22thermoelectrics.org	Barcelona (Spain)	Thermoelectric Academic							TECHNOLOGY?
Research 21 mining convention		20/09/2022	30/09/2022	Physical	https://www.research21.com/	Antwerp (Belgium)	Mining companies, Geological Survey, academics, SME							
WorldPM22		09/10/2022	13/10/2022	Physical	https://www.epma.com/2022/	Lyon (France)	PII community	Yes	-	EuroPMI sectoral Group meeting	11/12/2022	F. Neves	EPMA	
WorldPM22		09/10/2022	13/10/2022	Physical	https://www.epma.com/2022/	Lyon (France)	PII community	Yes	-	Industry Corner	?	F. Neves	EPMA	
EU-Latin America convention		2022, Nov		Physical	https://www.mineraplatform.eu/en/entrepreneur-america-convention-raw-materials									ASAMI
Raw Materials Week 2022 (every year in November)		2022, Nov		Physical										
1st START Webinar (LNEO)		2022, Feb		Online	START website									Project pres
1st START Webinar (LNEO)		2022, Feb		Online	START website									Technical pres
1st START Webinar (LNEO)		2022, Feb		Online	START website									Technical pres
GENERA 2022 (International Energy and Environment Fair)		21/02/2023	23/02/2023	Physical	http://www.thema.es/genera	Madrid	Energy and Environment							
Latineria		20/05/2023	24/05/2023	Physical	http://www.thema.es/latineria	Buenos Aires (Argentina)	Energy, Transport & logistic, Mining Technology and Industrie fair							
Jornadas Científico Técnicas del IMAE-ODI		2023, Jun?		Physical	http://www.imae.odi.gub.uy/	Montevideo (Uruguay)								Ester Bolinereu
EuropeanRawMat2023		11/06/2023	13/06/2023	Physical	https://www.eurochem.com/industry-forum-2023	Madrid (Spain)								
EPMA Fall seminar 2023		28/06/2023	29/06/2023	Hybrid	www.epma.com	San Sebastian (Spain)	PII community	-	-	Technical pres				EPMA
Sustainable Minerals '23		2023, Jul?		Physical	https://min.eurochem.com/sustainable-minerals-23/									
EPMA Summer School 2023		2023, Jul?		Physical	https://summerschool.epma.com/	Orleans (Germany)								F. Neves?
IRAWMA 2023		28/08/2023	02/09/2023	Physical	https://www.mineraplatform.eu/congress/	Athens (Greece)				The START project				EPMA
End START Webinar (LNEO)		2023, Sep?		Online										LNEO
European Conference on Thermoelectrics (ECT) 2023?		2023, Sep?		Physical	http://www.ec23thermoelectrics.org		Thermoelectric Academic							TECHNOLOGY?
EPMA event - Materials for Energy Transition		2023, Sep?		Physical										LNEO
European Roundtable on Sustainable Consumption and Production		2023, Sep?		Physical	https://ec.europa.eu/eip/	Wageningen, NL	Academic, wide							LNEO
Researcher Night 2023		20/09/2023	20/09/2023	Hybrid	https://materials-uk.co.uk/events/care-actions.ec.eu	Melny	Academic, wide							?
EuropM23		01/10/2023	04/10/2023	Physical	https://www.epma.com/2023/	Lisbon (Portugal)	PII community	Yes	-	Technical pres?				EPMA
Raw Materials Week 2023 (every year in November)		2023, Nov		Physical										
GENERA 2024 (International Energy and Environment Fair)		2024, Feb?		Physical	http://www.thema.es/genera	Madrid	Energy and Environment							
1st START Webinar (LNEO)		2024, Feb?		Online										Project pres
1st START Webinar (LNEO)		2024, Feb?		Online										Technical pres
EPMA Fall seminar 2024		2024, TBD		Hybrid	www.epma.com	TBD	PII community	-	-	Technical pres				EPMA
EPMA Fall seminar 2024		09/10/2024	09/10/2024	Physical	www.epma.com	Madrid (Spain)	PII community	Yes	-	Technical pres				EPMA
Conference on Industrial Technologies IndTech 2024		2024, Jun?		Physical	https://www.indtech2024.com/	Madrid (Spain)								
START Seminar		2024, Jun?		Physical	START website									Project pres
EPMA Summer School 2024		2024, Jun/Jul		Physical	https://summerschool.epma.com/	TBD	PII community	-	-	update on the START project				?
Sustainable Minerals '24		2024, Jul?		Physical	https://min.eurochem.com/sustainable-minerals-24/									
Researcher Night 2024		2024, Sep?		Hybrid	https://materials-uk.co.uk/events/care-actions.ec.eu	Melny	Academic, wide							?
ESMA 2024		2024, Sep?		Online	START website									Technical pres
IMM (Mining and Minerals Hall)		2024, Oct?		Physical	http://www.imm2024.com/	Seville	Mining							
CONAMA (biannual congress)		2024, Oct?		Physical	http://www.conama.com/	Madrid	Sustainability							Ester Bolinereu
1st START Webinar (LNEO)		2024, Nov?		Online										LNEO
Raw Materials Week 2024 (every year in November)		2024, Nov		Physical										
GENERA 2025 (International Energy and Environment Fair)		2025, Feb?		Physical	http://www.thema.es/genera	Madrid	Energy and Environment							
1st START Webinar (LNEO)		2025, Feb?		Online										Project pres
1st START Webinar (LNEO)		2025, Feb?		Online										Technical pres
EPMA Fall or HR seminar 2025		2025, TBD		Hybrid	www.epma.com	TBD	PII community	-	-	Technical pres				?
International Conference on Thermoelectrics (ICT) 2025		2025, Jun/Jul		Physical	www.epma.com	Sendai (Japan)	Thermoelectric Academic							?
EPMA Summer School 2025		2025, Jun/Jul		Physical	https://summerschool.epma.com/	TBD	PII community	-	-	to be considered for the following years				?
Sustainable Minerals '25		2025, Jul?		Physical	https://min.eurochem.com/sustainable-minerals-25/									
European Roundtable on Sustainable Consumption and Production		2025, Sep?		Physical	https://ec.europa.eu/eip/	TBD	Academic, wide							LNEO
1st START Webinar (LNEO)		2025, Sep?		Online										Technical pres
Researcher Night 2025		2025, Sep?		Hybrid	https://materials-uk.co.uk/events/care-actions.ec.eu	Melny	Academic, wide							?
EuropM25		14/09/2025	17/09/2025	Physical	https://www.epma.com/2025/	Glasgow (UK)	PII community	Yes	-	Technical pres				EPMA
Raw Materials Week 2025 (every year in November)		2025, Nov		Physical										
1st START Webinar (LNEO)		2025, Feb?		Online										Project pres
1st START Webinar (LNEO)		2025, Feb?		Online										Technical pres
GENERA 2026 (International Energy and Environment Fair)		2026, Feb?		Physical	http://www.thema.es/genera	Madrid	Energy and Environment							
EPMA Fall or HR seminar 2026		2026, TBD		Hybrid	www.epma.com	TBD	PII community	-	-	Technical pres				?
Final START event		2026, Mar		Physical	START website	Bussel?								Many
Final Training Workshop		2026, Apr		Physical	START website	TBD								Many
Other activities/Science Festival (TSD)				Physical										?
European Raw Materials Alliance (ERMA)				Physical	http://www.erma.eu/workshops/									
Energy Materials Industry Research Initiative (EMIRI)				Physical	https://www.emiri.eu/									

Figure 1: Printout of the START Events List Excel file.

The tool will be used all along the project, by updating the lines (the upcoming events) and reassessing the priorities continuously. Priorities are being initialised now: each relevant partner has been asked to fill the cells in a priority list, and then all opinions will be aggregated in a consortium-based priority. In this beginning stage, some upcoming events have been provisionally assigned high priority, whereas others, for which the consortium was not ready with the materials (branding had yet to be defined, leaflets, posters and rollups are being developed at the time of the writing of this DCP) have been de-prioritised, but in the case of recurring events they will be reconsidered for 2023 and successive years. Some recurring events, and presumably high priority, are these:

- European Conference on Thermoelectrics (ECT) conference series

- GENERA (International Energy and Environment Fair)
- Raw Materials Week
- EIT Raw Materials summit
- EU-Latin America partnership on Raw Materials
- EU Green week
- EPMA's EuroPM Powder Metallurgy yearly Congress & Exhibition (WorldPM in 2022)
- EPMA's seminars (HIP, Functional Materials)
- Sustainable Minerals

5.3 RULES FOR PUBLICATION

All partners are requested to be proactive in bringing information about the project, its approach and results to the biggest possible audience. This means that publications are welcome at any time, provided they respect the basic rules that will make them useful for the project's cause.

All publications will have to:

- Be agreed in advance with the WP6 leader (EPMA) and the Coordinator
- Be prepared by the relevant partners considering the need of dissemination but also the necessary confidentiality to guarantee a successful exploitation of project activities (e.g., patenting when applicable)
- Respect project branding guidelines
- Respect third party copyrights (for instance, for pictures)
- Be approved actively or passively (when relevant deadlines for consortium editing or opposing expire) by the consortium, through its ExCom and the Coordinator
- Whenever possible and to a reasonable extent, be followed up and evaluated in terms of apparent impact (audience, views, etc.) and also qualitatively in terms of interest raised

5.3.1 DELIVERABLES

For deliverables, a procedure has been established in the first meeting of the ExCom in concomitance with the KickOff Meeting, on 20st June 2022.

The content must be finalized and submitted to the ExCom 4 weeks before the deadline and the final validation must be done 2 weeks before the deadline (scheme in Figure 2 below).

This procedure will be applied irrespectively of the type of publicity given to the deliverable.

Figure 2: Procedure for approval of deliverables before submission as approved in the first ExCom meeting on 21st June 2022.

This is the list of deliverables connected with WP6:

D6.1 - Creation of the project website, graphical identity and other online tools (M02): This deliverable describes the project's website, addresses the inherent need of the project to develop the START graphical identity, together with all the other online tools designed to support objectives of WP6.

D6.2 - Dissemination and Communication Plan (M03): Document outlining the most efficient strategy and means for implementing the dissemination and communication activities.

D6.3 - Dissemination, outreach and clustering activities (M06 and repeated every six months): Report to be prepared on a 6-month basis, describing all the dissemination, communication, outreach and clustering activities with other EU projects and initiatives that have been developed and implemented and plans on how to proceed.

D6.4 - Training activities (M12 and repeated every 12 months): Report to be prepared on a 12-month basis describing the training activities implemented.

D.6.5 - Final Event (M46): Final event conference report.

As all those deliverables are "PU – Public", the approval phase is particularly important to avoid breaching of necessary confidentiality on technical matters.

5.3.2 GENERAL PUBLICATIONS

Prior notice of any planned publication shall be given to the other Parties at least 15 calendar days before the publication. Any objection to the planned publication shall be made in accordance with the Grant Agreement by written notice to the Coordinator and to the Party or Parties proposing the dissemination within 15 calendar days after receipt of the notice.

The objections will be discussed among the interested parties in order to solve the issues within the time frame for publication.

Within the same time frame all amendments received will be discussed and the publication will be reviewed.

If no objection is made within the time limit stated above, the publication is permitted "as it is".

5.3.3 PUBLICATIONS ON PROJECT WEBSITE

The contents to be published on the website will have to be approved following the standard procedure for general publications.

The accompanying text can be published by the website master partner (EPMA), upon previous consent by the coordinator.

Among these contents, the Newsletter (see paragraph 5.7) will have a special role, having a regular cadence, but with a clear need to make sure that all Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) are respected.

5.3.4 PUBLICATIONS ON PROJECT'S SOCIAL MEDIA

The contents to be published on social media accounts will have to be approved following the standard procedure for general publications.

The accompanying text can be published by the social media master partner (EPMA, LPRC or ASGMI), upon previous consent by the coordinator.

All partners are encouraged to reshare on their social media (also with personal accounts) and/or websites the news and documents published by the project, and to give data about the impact of their posts.

5.3.5 PUBLICATIONS ON EXTERNAL MEDIA – MAGAZINES, JOURNALS, PRESENTATIONS IN EVENTS

External media will be particularly important for general communication, although in some cases also scientific dissemination could happen via these media. The contents to be published on external media will have to be approved following the standard procedure for general publications.

This includes:

- Scientific papers to be included in a scientific journal or a magazine, a scientific book, conference proceedings or similar, either printed or web based.
- News items to be published in magazines, or newspapers, either printed or web based, including websites.
- Oral presentations at congresses, conferences: the approval will concern the slides and/or the text of the presentation

5.4 PROJECT GRAPHICAL IDENTITY

The project's graphical identity has been already developed and reported in deliverable D6.1 ("Creation of the project website, graphical identity and other online tools"), submitted on 29th July 2022. It must be used in all official project documents, including deliverables.

It includes:

- Colour branding
- Logo
- Fonts to be used in documents
- Templates
- A basic E-Mail signature.

5.5 PROJECT WEBSITE

The project's website has been already developed and reported in deliverable D6.1 ("Creation of the project website, graphical identity and other online tools"), submitted on 29th July 2022.

Its address is

www.START-HEproject.com

Another site address, www.HE-START.eu, is automatically redirected to the main address.

The website will be updated in terms of contents and new features may be introduced (new pages, widgets, etc.) if deemed useful.

5.6 SOCIAL MEDIA

The project's social media accounts have been already created and reported in deliverable D6.1 ("Creation of the project website, graphical identity and other online tools"), submitted on 29th July 2022. The social media activated are:

- Twitter (partner responsible: LPRC)
- LinkedIn (partner responsible: EPMA)
- YouTube (partner responsible: EPMA)
- Twitch (partner responsible: LPRC)
- SlideShare (partner responsible: ASGMI)

In addition to these, an account on the Zenodo service¹, the Open Data service created by CERN within the OpenAIRE project in 2013, that also offers the creation of a DOI (Digital Object Identifier) number, has been created ([Sustainable energy harvesting systems based on innovative mine waste recycling | Zenodo](https://zenodo.org/record/6444441)) by LNEG and will be used, in parallel with SlideShare, to get open access to the START documents.

Social media will be used to engage the audience, bring them to the website, and in general to disseminate and communicate (also to the wider public) about START activities, results and partners.

5.7 START NEWSLETTER

The project will have a Newsletter, published on its website and social media every 6 months, starting from Issue 1 at M06. To give more appeal to the newsletter, the consortium will choose a name that is suggesting that the content will not be just related to START but will be strictly connected with the sustainability solutions imagined. The name will be decided among the consortium before the first issue is prepared, thus within the deadline of 30th September 2022.

The information conveyed in the various issues of the newsletter will in fact include:

- General information about START, thermoelectric materials, energy harvesting from waste heat, and linked sustainability topics, including state-of-the-art documents and scientific reviews
- Updates on project activities
- Updates on project events and other dissemination topics, with invitation to join events where START will be featured
- Description of consortium partners (typically 2 per issue)
- All information on the various ways to keep informed about START (links to website, social media, link to the contact and subscription forms, etc.)

¹ <https://zenodo.org/>

It is likely that the first issue will not be much longer than 4 A4 pages, but with the progress in the project, and the need to stimulate exploitation, the length will probably increase.

Being completely public, the information in the Newsletter must be duly checked in order to avoid IPR management issues.

The distribution will be wide, but a part of it will be based on a list of subscribers. To create the list, the website tool for registration will be used and social media posts will attract new subscribers to the website tool. In case the approach based on the list is not effective in generating subscriptions, other possibilities will be considered, including the choice of leaving the newsletter freely downloadable without registration.

5.8 VIDEOS

At least 5 videos will be produced during the project:

- 2 short videos (0.5-1 min), one at the start of the project to raise awareness and one at the end to summarise results. The language should be suitable for a wider audience; animations or cartoons could be used to attract non-specialists. One video at M04 (September 2022), one at M48 (May 2026).
- 2 longer videos (but still not too long, max 3 min) during the project, focusing on project topics and activities. The target should be more to groups 2-3, i.e., scientists, engineers, and entrepreneurs. Both videos are due at M48 (May 2026)
- 1 detailed video (about 5 min) at mid project (M24, May 2024), highlighting the results of the first part of the project.

Other videos could be produced, like:

- Interviews with key partners, describing the project (coordinator) or specific topics
- Recording of presentations given in events
- Short ads for specific events or for the “serious game”

EPMA will be taking care of producing the videos but will ask all relevant partners to help by delivering videos, images, and text.

The videos will be hosted on YouTube and Twitch, will be embedded in the START website, and posted on other social media like LinkedIn and Twitter.

The KPIs decided for these tools are basically views. A minimum of 100 views per video is the base KPI, and an overall average above 200 views/video is an additional KPI. Clearly, the different social media analysis tools will allow collecting even further information about the audience.

5.9 WEBINARS / SEMINARS / WORKSHOPS

Beside participation in conferences and other events where consortium partners will present, the consortium will also organise START-labelled events, both physical and online.

These will be special dissemination seminars and presentations, connected to the project, like webinars or in person seminars, on specific project-related topics, with contributions from the consortium and selected external speakers.

In particular, at least the following events will be organised:

- 2 short webinars per year (starting from 2023). These will be organised directly by LNEG, will have a duration of 1-1.5 h (1-2 speakers) and will be used to address specific topics within the project's scope, like thermoelectrics, thermal waste recovery, etc.
- An in-person seminar around mid-term, with more speakers (order of magnitude 10), duration of at least 1 full day. This will be hosted in a convenient venue where interesting lab or field visits can be organised for participants.
- A final in-person event. A specific task is dedicated to this activity (Task 6.5 from M42 to M48). A final conference will be organised at the end of the project, likely in Brussels, as a main dissemination event showcasing the successes achieved over the four years of the project. The details of the event (type of event, audience, key-note speakers...) will be determined during the project (starting around M42). The final conference will try to be organised back-to-back with other mayor relevant event to ensure as large audience as possible.)

In order to advertise these events and achieve the expected participation of at least 100 per event, ads on dedicated printed or online magazines (e.g., Journal of Degraded and Mining Lands Management, Journal of Environmental Management, Environmental Earth Sciences, Environmental Science and Pollution Research, Mine Water and the Environment...) will be used.

5.10 SCIENTIFIC PUBLICATIONS AND PARTICIPATION TO SCIENTIFIC EVENTS

Publications and presentations in conferences, seminars and congresses are strongly encouraged: all consortium partners should try to organise a technical participation in an event to disseminate a part of the work carried out in START. This will broaden the audience for the project topics and in the end will create the condition for successful exploitation.

Thus, maybe with some exceptions, we expect that during the course of the project almost all partners will submit papers in relevant conferences, congresses, exhibitions, and scientific journals to give information on the results of the START project.

As EPMA, WP6 leader, is also naturally organising events, mainly for the powder metallurgy community in Europe, it will be easy for the consortium to take part in relevant EPMA events like:

- The EuroPM and/or WorldPM Congress and Exhibition series. Here, in addition to technical presentations, project booths can be organised, at reduced cost (internal costs for EPMA).
- The EPMA technical seminars by sectors (in particular on Functional Materials, Hot Isostatic Pressing, that are directly related to project activities).
- Sectoral group meetings, namely of the European Functional Materials Sectoral Group (EuroFM), and the European Hot Isostatic Pressing Sectoral Group (EuroHIP), but also of the Environment, Health, Quality and Safety Working Group (EHQS) that deals with sustainability and all connected issues.

In addition to those, a list of other events has been created (see paragraph 5.2) to collect and evaluate many possible events where START could feature somehow. As explained in the mentioned paragraph, the priorities on participation to the various events will be agreed among consortium members; a good balance will be sought between:

- the different sectors that can be interested to the project (mining, thermoelectric materials, powder metallurgy, energy harvesting, sustainability, general industry), and
- the different target audience groups.

5.11 OTHER PUBLICATIONS

Addressing communities that are outside those already covered by the consortium members activities and by the standard journals, magazines and conferences/events is rather important for an innovative project like START. For this reason, the plan is to try addressing external communities by publishing well balanced papers and articles in more general magazines, or news services/websites.

The Horizon Results service will host project's results, and this is already a public platform available to everyone interested in the topic. Attempts will be made to have articles about START published on the EU news services like the Horizon Magazine. But the consortium will also find suitable generic magazines, like for instance the Open Access Government² magazine, that has an "Energy" section and is distributed to a wide variety of readers, including policymakers.

These articles will likely not be published for free, so some budget had been allocated in the proposal.

5.12 PARTICIPATION IN INDUSTRIAL EVENTS

EPMA and any consortium partners will advertise the project by taking part in at least 2 external events and exhibitions per year to further communicate the public results of the project.

A project booth will be organised, similarly to what will happen in the EuroPM exhibitions. Within the booth posters, banners, leaflets and promotional consumables will be available. Where possible, presentations about the project will be given.

Participation in industrial events will also be subject to evaluation by priorities as explained in paragraph and a balance between the different sectors that can be interested to the project (mining, thermoelectric materials, powder metallurgy, energy harvesting, sustainability, general industry) will be sought.

5.13 PARTICIPATION IN OTHER EVENTS

The consortium will investigate the chance of taking part in Science Festivals and Fairs.

This would be useful to communicate the scope of the project and improve the awareness of the energy and sustainability issues in the public, i.e., to target group 4. These events need preparation of simple materials, and possibly practical experiences that can be demonstrated easily to people with presumably low scientific knowledge, including sometimes children.

Due to the nature of the events, participation is best organised in a country where more consortium partners are present, so for instance Portugal, Spain, etc.

² <https://www.openaccessgovernment.org/>

A list of possible festivals and fairs will be included in the START events list, with participation possible starting from 2023. Among possible events we can list now:

- Madrid es Ciencia³ (last edition happened in March 2022)
- Festival Internacional de Ciência⁴ (the 2022 edition will be on 10th-16th October)
- Encontro Ciência⁵ (last edition happened in May 2022)
- Semana da Ciência e da Tecnologia⁶ (last edition happened in November 2021)
- Festival della Scienza⁷ (the 2022 edition will take place on 20th October – 1st November)
- the European Researchers' Night, held normally on the last Friday of September each year

5.14 MATERIALS FOR BOOTHS/PHYSICAL DISTRIBUTION

Some material will be produced during the project in order to be shown and in some cases distributed to interested people in physical events. The latter may be informative material (leaflets, for instance) but may also be small gadgets that carry at least the project logo and thus might attract people to search for more information later.

The informative material will also be used in its digital version for the website and for other uses.

5.14.1 LEAFLET(S)

Leaflets will be produced both in pdf and in print. They will generally be in A5 size, two-sided. The final version may need more room, so a 4-page A5 sized leaflet will probably be prepared. All this material will be available for download from the website and distributed at physical events. As a general «lean» approach, though, printed copies will be limited in number and digital download will be encouraged to reduce paper waste. QR codes will be offered to scan, with direct link to the downloadable materials.

If a partner needs to print a specific leaflet, the printable files will be made available (InDesign format).

These will be the different versions foreseen for the leaflets:

- Version 1 at start
- Version 2 at midterm (M24, May 2024)
- Version 3, final, at project end M46 (March 2026) for distribution during the final event and other concluding events

5.14.2 ROLLER BANNER(S)

Roller banners, or rollups, are self-standing “vertical” elements (typically 2 m high, 0.85 m wide) that usually show rather generic info about the project, for instance the logo of the project and of the partners, diagrams with explanation of the project’s workflow and basic principles, images

³ <https://www.ifema.es/madrid-es-ciencia>

⁴ <https://www.fica.pt/>

⁵ <http://www.encontrociencia.pt/2022/>

⁶ <https://www.cienciaviva.pt/semanact/2021/>

⁷ <http://www.festivalscienza.eu/site/en/home.html>

showing devices or parts, etc., accompanied by simple text that can be read in a short time (e.g., while walking in front of a booth). They are normally used in booths or in the rooms when a project event is happening, so that the project logo is continuously visible for the participants.

It is planned to print initially a generic roller banner with the basic information about the project, that will be used along the project every time that a project booth will be set up in an event.

At least one more roller banner will be prepared, after midterm, with some highlights of results obtained until then.

The banners will be reusable, but wear and tear (for instance during shipping) could lead to the need to reprint them. In that case, a review of the content could be done.

5.14.3 POSTER(S)

Posters can be of different approach. A poster could just show the project logo, or consortium partners. Others could be more verbose, and explain more about the project approach, specific results, etc. It is believed that at least 3-4 different posters may be needed for exhibiting in booth or as poster presentations in some event. EPMA will take care of preparing the graphic files for the posters, and printing those needed for the events where EPMA will take part; but all partners will be able to access the printable files and use them in events where they go on their own, by printing them (the cost for shipping is quite likely higher than a reprint). Also, wear and tear are very probable, so new copies will likely be printed during the project.

5.14.4 CONSUMABLES

Gadgets will be considered, to be distributed at exhibitions. Examples: pens, bags, USB sticks with project info, etc. The gadgets will have project's logo and website and if possible, should be in line with the project's approach, recalling sustainability aspects.

5.15 SERIOUS ONLINE GAME

The online game, developed in WP7, Task 7.1 (it constitutes D7.2, due at M44) will focus on raw materials usage, sustainability and circular economy to be used for capacity building activities targeting adult players. Serious games are particularly effective for capacity building as they are fun to play and motivate users to absorb the concepts being communicated. There are already several circular economy online games, but they are designed for children. The START serious game will be designed for public and private stakeholders within the value chains of mining, heavy industry and maritime industry. It will allow for players to:

- (i) select and apply several circular economy options involving critical materials and mine waste recycling and
- (ii) assess results in terms of damages / gains along selected SDGs (Sustainable Development Goals).

The game will build on findings from START research outcomes, translating them in layman's terms. To build on a common structure, the plan is to use the same character that will be developed for the comics (see paragraph 5.15.1), whose provisional name is "START the robot". This will make the game more appealing to the young people.

This task will also include testing the game within the consortium and ensuring its use throughout Europe during at least the last 6 months of the project. The game will be made available free of charge after the end of the project.

Examples of relevant serious games in related domains are listed as follows:

- <https://inchainge.com/business-games/tbc/>
- <https://resourcity.vito.be/en>
- https://games.focusgames.co.uk/bioeconomy_game/game
- <https://www.bettergeoedu.com/>
- <https://recyclegame.eu/>
- <https://eitrawmaterials.eu/eit-rm-academy/online-learning/learning-resources/>

The game will be disseminated by using the website and the social media: gameplay videos, call to challenges, live streaming of playing sessions, live play at exhibitions, etc.

5.15.1 START COMICS

Communication in START includes information and promotion activities to increase the visibility of the project and therefore is aimed at a more generic target (public opinion, the media). Some of the subjects developed in START could not be of general knowledge, hence simple clarifications and explanations for a generic audience would be very useful. The communication targets are common citizens: while not having a direct interest in the project's results, they can still benefit from it in terms of quality of life, opportunities for the territory, etc.

The used media for communication are strategically important as they can amplify START communication, giving strong resonance to the project actions. Hence, this communication strategy will be composed of a comics story, with a character that will guide the reader into the START contents (Table 2). This character is being drafted and its provisional name is "START the robot". This comics story will be animated as well, in order to be used in communication media, e.g., YouTube.

Table 2: Plan to develop START comics.

ACTION	Q1 (Sep22-Nov22)	Q2 (Dec22-Feb23)	Q3 (Mar23-May23)	Q4 (Jun23-Aug23)
Content Development				
Character Development				
Story board				
Drawing pages				
Animation				
Tests & Release				

5.16 TRAINING

Training is seen as an important part of dissemination, as it can improve the awareness about the project topics, and at the same time, especially for young researchers or industrial employees, it can create durable networks that will likely grow in the future as the trained people advance in their careers. For already experienced researchers and industrial employees, the knowledge gained in the training about the project topics will be useful to steer strategic decision in the direction of a larger use of thermoelectric materials and waste heat recovery devices.

The training activity within START, that constitutes a separate task (T6.3 from M12 to M48) aims in fact to ensure the transfer of high-value knowledge already present within the consortium and that will be generated by the project to promote learning opportunities and building capacities with and for young scientists.

The plan is to make use of established and new training activities, to funnel knowledge to students, young engineers, and experts.

At the beginning of the activity for training, that is due to start on M12, a strategic document on how to present, promote, call, recruit and orient and mentoring young students and researchers into the project will be prepared. This will be ready by M13.

In terms of activity, three main event lines specific for training (in addition to all other seminars, webinars and presentations that will certainly be useful to complement training activities) will be followed.

5.16.1 START LECTURES DURING THE EPMA PM SUMMER SCHOOL.

The EPMA Residential Summer School is an established training activity that EPMA has undertaken since 1998. In June 2022 the 20th edition was run in Ciudad Real (Spain). It is a 1-week full course about powder metallurgy, where info about most PM technologies and materials are given. The trainees are usually PhD students, or young engineers from companies. Normally an average of 55 students are hosted by a fellow institution (a university or a research centre, mostly), where lectures are given by expert speakers from all over Europe, and lab experiences are organised by the hosting institution. It is planned to include in every year's edition within the time frame of START, i.e., from 2023 to 2025, a lecture or lab experience given by START experts. This requires the preparation of a lecture or lab activity, updated every year, about START topics. Possibly, in the first edition (in 2023) a general presentation about thermoelectric materials and the project itself will be given; in later editions the best option would be to prepare a little experience with thermoelectric materials, or better heat recovery devices, so that the trainees can get a direct insight in the applications as well.

5.16.2 ASGMI WORKSHOPS

ASGMI has significant experience working with Mining Environmental Liabilities. In the past, several workshops and events have been organized on this topic⁸. ASGMI will develop learning material based on the already existing products & experience and will add new information and results from START (mainly from WP 2). The objective is to hold a free online seminar open to bachelor and master's degree young students where they can interact with the researchers, ask questions and learn details of the project.

⁸ <https://asgmi.org/grupo-de-expertos-en-pasivosambientales-mineros-2/>

5.16.3 FINAL TRAINING WORKSHOP

A final Training Workshop will be organised on M47 for scientists and industry members. The event will take place in a convenient location, to be defined. As it will happen after the project's final event in Brussels, this latter event will be used to strongly advertise the training event.

As it is a final training workshop, the programme will contain detailed information on the materials and technologies developed during the project, clearly without forgetting the confidentiality needed for the IPR management on the subjects. Lecturers from the consortium will give presentation to external participants. Due to the project approach, it will be important to focus on sustainability of the developed know-how, in order to attract also trainees who are not materials experts or technologists.

5.17 CLUSTERING

The objective of the clustering activity, that constitutes task T6.4 and will begin at M03 to end at M48, will be building a comprehensive cluster for the dissemination of the project. The main idea is to create an effective strategy to identify similar and interesting projects and find synergies to create value, avoid duplications and strengthen and maximize the START project results impact.

In fact, projects which share a common theme or address similar challenges can form a cluster initiative and deliver shared strategic outputs.

The START project will be seeking to enhance links and synergies with similar projects, like ongoing H2020 or new Horizon Europe projects, the EIT-related Knowledge Innovation Centres (EIT RawMaterials, Innoenergy and Climate KIC) and other relevant projects and initiatives.

The deliverable D6.3 "Dissemination, outreach and clustering" due at M06 will further explain the concept and strategy for the clustering activities. ASGMI with the support of all partners will identify the project coordinators of the selected projects & initiatives. Mapping the synergies among the different projects will maximize the impact and contribute to have a more efficient and strong European Innovation. As a first point a database contenting interesting project and initiatives will be created. This database will be fed by different resources such as:

- the Community Research and Development Information Service (CORDIS)
- the EIT (including the KICs on Raw Materials, Innoenergy & Climate KIC)
- the internal community (partners in the consortium and its members)

Then, a series of online short meetings will be established with the Project Coordinators or key people and the START project coordinator and/or the Communication WP leader.

Key events and meetings will be also essential to identify and establish good connections: the people from the initiatives in the clustering database, likely belonging to the audience target Groups 2 and 3, but hopefully in some cases also from Group 1, will be invited to the relevant events organized by START (seminars, webinars, trainings, final event) ensuring dedicated time for networking and collaboration.

5.18 CONTINUOUS EVALUATION OF D&C PERFORMANCE

5.18.1 KPIS

KPIs are “a quantifiable measure of performance over time for a specific objective”. Although they are not the same as metrics, in the case of measuring the performance of a website or a social media that is normal.

To assess the dissemination, START will collect metrics from the website, and the social media, and will compare some selected KPIs to chosen reference values that the project expects to meet of the years. A list of the KPIs imagined, with their reference values, is given in Table 3.

Table 3: KPIs considered for D&C activities.

Tool	KPI	Reference value
Project website	Visitors	Year 1: 2000 Year 4: 4000
Twitter	Followers	Year 1: 1000 End: 2500
LinkedIn	Followers	End:800
Videos	Views	More than 100/video Average 200
Newsletters	Addressees	More than 500/issue
Webinars/ seminars/ workshop	Audience	100
Serious online game	Visitors	300
Other publications	Reach	More than 400000

According to previous experiences, as already shown in deliverable D6.1 (“Creation of the project website, graphical identity and other online tools”), an Excel file will be used to collect the data of dissemination performance on social media, in order to quantify the audience reached and the interest arisen.

This is located on the START SharePoint (its address is [START/Work Packages/WP6 - Dissemination and communication/START Monitoring Tool for Online Dissemination.xlsx](#)) and will contain all the details collected from the different social media posts and contents, and from the website. A preview of the structure of the file is visible in the screenshot of Figure 3.

- specific partners that will be invited if their participation will be useful in the discussion, for instance if their activity is required in the following months.

The meetings will be at least 2 per semester; EPMA will take care of preparing the minutes and distributing them to participants, in addition to uploading them to the SharePoint under WP6/Meetings.

Other smaller group meetings may be called for specific discussions, like the detailed organisation of a particular event where only some partners are involved.

5.18.3 CONTINUOUS REPORTING ON FUNDING&TENDER WEBSITE

The WP Leader (EPMA) will be responsible of regularly updating the information on Dissemination and Communication in the relevant section in the project's Continuous Reporting on the Funding&Tender website. There are three pages dedicated to these topics on the portal: Publications, Dissemination and Communication (Figure 4, Figure 5 and Figure 6).

At the latest, an update will need to be made before the end of each reporting period, as at each periodic report, all the information present in the Continuous Reporting section will be automatically compiled to create Part A of the Periodic Technical Report.

The screenshot displays the 'Project Continuous Report' interface. At the top, there is a navigation bar with icons for Project Summary, Researchers involved in the project, Deliverables, Milestones, Critical Risks, Publications, Dissemination activities, Standards, Patents (IPR), Communication activities, Datasets, Financial support to 3rd parties, Beneficiaries Feedback, Impact, and Results. The 'Publications' icon is highlighted.

Below the navigation bar, the 'Publications' section is visible. It includes a checkbox for 'This project does not currently have any scientific publications' and a section for 'Suggested publications from OpenAIRE (0 pending publications and 0 discarded publications)'. A table lists project publications, with one entry shown:

Type	Title	Authors	Title of the Journal or equivalent	Number	Peer-reviewed	Was the publication available in open access through the repository at the time of publication	PID (Publisher version of record)	PID of deposited publication	Actions
1	Other	GREEN ENERGY HARVESTIN	START project		False	True			Export to Excel Add Publication

At the bottom of the page, there is a 'Validate' button.

Figure 4: Screenshot of the page dedicated to Publications on the Funding&Tender portal.

The screenshot displays the 'Dissemination Activities' page. At the top, there is a navigation bar with the following tabs: Project Summary, Researchers involved in the project, Deliverables, Milestones, Critical Risks, Publications, Dissemination activities (highlighted with a green checkmark), Standards, Patents (IPR), Communication Activities, Datasets, Financial support to 3rd parties, Beneficiaries Feedback, Impact, and Results. Below the navigation bar, the 'Dissemination Activities' section is visible, featuring a 'SAVE' button and a checkbox for 'There is no dissemination activity for this project yet'. A table for adding dissemination activities is present, with columns: Dissemination activity name, What? Type of dissemination activity, Who? Target audience (Choose one or more items), Why? (Max 200 characters), Status, and Actions. A 'Validate' button is located at the bottom right of the page.

Figure 5: Screenshot of the page dedicated to Dissemination on the Funding&Tender portal.

The screenshot displays the 'Communications Activities' page. At the top, there is a navigation bar with the following tabs: Project Summary, Researchers involved in the project, Deliverables, Milestones, Critical Risks, Publications, Dissemination activities, Standards, Patents (IPR), Communication Activities (highlighted with a green checkmark), Datasets, Financial support to 3rd parties, Beneficiaries Feedback, Impact, and Results. Below the navigation bar, the 'Communications Activities' section is visible, featuring a 'SAVE' button and a checkbox for 'There are no communication activities for this project yet'. A table for adding communication activities is present, with the text 'No communication activities added' displayed. A 'Validate' button is located at the bottom right of the page.

Figure 6: Screenshot of the page dedicated to Communication on the Funding&Tender portal.

5.19 UPDATE OF THE DCP

A review of the DCP will be undertaken at least at:

- Midterm (M24)
- End of project (for “legacy” activities)

In case urgent systemic issues affect dissemination or communication, in one or more activities, an urgent review will be asked by the WP Leader upon agreement with the ExCom.